

A. Medicine and Health

Nov 1, 2020 (JAMA Cardio.)

Association of Troponin Levels With Mortality in Italian Patients Hospitalized With Coronavirus Disease 2019: Results of a Multicenter Study
Carlo Mario Lombardi, Valentina Carubelli, Annamaria Iorio et al.
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamacardio.2020.3538>

This cohort study of patients with coronavirus disease 2019 who were hospitalized in cardiology units in Italy assesses the association of troponin levels at admission with patient outcomes.

Nov 1, 2020 (JAMA Int Med.)

Prone Positioning in Awake, Nonintubated Patients With COVID-19 Hypoxemic Respiratory Failure
Alison E. Thompson, Benjamin L. Ranard, Ying Wei et al.
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2020.3030>

This cohort study investigates whether the prone position is associated with improved oxygenation and decreased risk for intubation in spontaneously breathing patients with severe COVID-19 hypoxaemic respiratory failure.

Nov 1, 2020 (JAMA Int Med.)

The Exclusion of Older Persons From Vaccine and Treatment Trials for Coronavirus Disease 2019—Missing the Target
Benjamin K. I. Helfand, Margaret Webb, Sarah L. Gartaganis et al.
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2020.5084>

This cross-sectional study evaluates the risk of exclusion for older adults in randomized clinical trials for treatment and vaccine interventions in COVID-19.

Oct 28, 2020 (JCLA)

Laboratory markers associated with COVID-19 progression in patients with or without comorbidity: A retrospective study
Zaishu Chen, Furong Zhang, Weihua Hu et al.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/jcla.23644>

The authors performed a multicentre retrospective study on 836 COVID-19 patients to investigate the utility of laboratory markers for COVID-19 progression in patients with different medical conditions. They found that lactate dehydrogenase was a reliable predictor associated with COVID-19 severity and mortality in patients with different medical conditions.

Oct 28, 2020 (Adv. Matter)

SARS-CoV-2 RBD Neutralizing Antibody Induction is Enhanced by Particulate Vaccination.

Huang, W.-C., Zhou, S., He, X. et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202005637>

In this article, the authors discuss particulate presentation strategies for the receptor-binding domain (RBD) immunogen to strongly induce neutralizing antibody responses against SARS-CoV-2. They show that rapid conversion of recombinant RBD into particulate form via admixing with liposomes containing cobalt-porphyrin-phospholipid (CoPoP) potentially enhances the functional antibody response.

Oct 23, 2020 (J of Parental and Enteral Nutrition)

Clinical Nutrition Research and the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Scoping Review of the ASPEN COVID-19 Task Force on Nutrition Research

Jeffrey I. Mechanick, Salvatore Carbone, Roland N. Dickerson et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/jpen.2036>

This scoping review by the American Society for Parenteral and Enteral Nutrition COVID-19 Nutrition Task Force aimed to examine nutrition research and identify knowledge gaps applicable to the COVID-19 pandemic. Epidemiological/mechanistic relationships between nutrition and COVID-19 were reviewed and results mapped to the Population, Intervention, Comparator, Outcome, and Time (PICO-T) questions. Nutrition topics meriting urgent research included food insecurity/societal infrastructure and transcultural factors (pre-COVID-19); cardiac-based chronic disease, pediatrics, nutrition support, and hospital infrastructure; dietitian nutritionist counselling; and malnutrition and management. Knowledge gaps were discovered for PICO-T questions. In conclusion, areas for urgent nutrition research were identified, particularly using RCT design to improve nutrition care for patients before, during, and after COVID-19.

Oct 22, 2020 (Investigative Otolaryngology)

Evaluation of predictive value of olfactory dysfunction, as a screening tool for COVID-19

Romero-Gameros, CA, Waizel-Haiat, S, Mendoza-Zubieta, V, et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/lio2.482>

This cross-sectional, observational, and pro-elective study was performed in a tertiary care hospital to determine the diagnostic yield of the smell dysfunction as a screening tool for COVID-19. A Self-Perception Questionnaire and psychophysical olfactory test (POT) were applied to 139 participants. The authors found that although there is a strong association between olfactory dysfunction and COVID-19, it is not an efficient screening tool and should not be considered as a single diagnostic instrument.

B. Science and Engineering

October 29, 2020 (Applied Soft Computing)

InstaCovNet-19: A deep learning classification model for the detection of COVID-19 patients using Chest X-ray

Anunay Gupta, Anjum, Shreyansh Gupta et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2020.106859>

In this paper, an integrated stacked deep convolution network InstaCovNet-19 is proposed. The proposed model makes use of various pre-trained models such as ResNet101, Xception, InceptionV3, MobileNet, and NASNet. The proposed model detects COVID-19 and pneumonia by identifying the abnormalities in chest X-ray images. The proposed model achieves an accuracy of 99.08% on 3 class (COVID-19, Pneumonia, Normal) classification and an accuracy of 99.53% on 2 class (COVID, NON-COVID) classification.

October 28, 2020 (Computers in Biology and Medicine)

The importance of standardisation – COVID-19 CT & Radiograph Image Data Stock for deep learning purpose

Krzysztof Misztal, Agnieszka Pocha, Martyna Durak-Kozica et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combiomed.2020.104092>

The authors propose a new dataset, COVID-19 CT and Radiograph Image Data Stock. It contains both CT and radiograph samples of COVID-19 lung findings and combines them with additional data to ensure a sufficient number of diverse COVID-19-negative samples. They aim to create a public pool of CT and radiograph images of lungs to increase the efficiency of distinguishing COVID-19 disease from pneumonia and healthy chest. They hope that the creation of this dataset would allow standardisation of the approach taken for training deep neural networks for COVID-19 classification and eventually for building more reliable models.

October 22, 2020 (Materials Chemistry and Physics)

Review on 3D printing: Fight against COVID-19

Bankole I. Oladapo, Sikiru O. Ismail, Temitope D. Afolalu et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2020.123943>

This is a review of the work done on solving COVID-19 with 3D printing. The use of bio-macromolecules antiviral respiratory assistance and other medical devices have improved the survival rate. A bio-cellular face shield with relative comfortability made of bio-macromolecules polymerized polyvinyl chloride (BPVC) and other biomaterials produced with 3D printers are described.

October 15, 2020 (Results in Physics)

Study of global dynamics of COVID-19 via a new mathematical model

Rahim ud Din, Aly R. Seadway, Kamal Shah et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rinp.2020.103468>

This paper focuses on the mathematical modeling and transmission mechanism of COVID-19 using a new type epidemic four-compartmental model that is susceptible, exposed, infected and recovered (SEIR), which describes the dynamics of COVID-19 under convex incidence rate. We simulate the results by using a nonstandard finite difference method (NSFDS).

October 8, 2020 (Computers in Biology and Medicine)

Multi-task deep learning based CT imaging analysis for COVID-19 pneumonia: Classification and segmentation

Amine Amyar, Romain Modzelewski, Hua Li et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combiomed.2020.104037>

This paper presents an automatic classification segmentation tool for screening COVID-19 pneumonia using chest CT imaging. They propose a multitask deep learning model to identify COVID-19 patient and segment COVID-19 lesion from chest CT images. Three learning tasks: segmentation, classification and reconstruction are jointly performed with different datasets. The aim is to improve both segmentation and classification performances and to deal with the problems of small data because each task can have a relatively small dataset. The obtained results show a dice coefficient higher than 0.88 for the segmentation and an area under the ROC curve higher than 97%.

C. Social Sciences, Humanities and Public Policies

October 17, 2020 (Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization)

Poverty and Economic Dislocation Reduce Compliance with COVID-19 Shelter-in-Place Protocols

Austin L. Wright, Konstantin Sonin, Jesse Driscoll et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jebo.2020.10.008>

in the US, residents of low-income areas complied with shelter-in-place ordinances less than their counterparts in areas with stronger economic levels. Novel results on the local impact of the 2020 CARES Act suggest stimulus transfers that addressed economic dislocation caused by the COVID-19 pandemic significantly increased social distancing.

October 12, 2020 (Journal of Innovation & Knowledge)

All that glitters is not gold. The rise of gaming in the COVID-19 pandemic

M. Ángeles López-Cabarcos, Domingo Ribeiro-Soriano, Juan Piñeiro-Chousac.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2020.10.004>

At the start of the outbreak, the financial markets collapsed, although not all sectors suffered equally. The gaming and eSports industry prospered during the pandemic. Using a logit–probit model, they analyze the relationship

between financial and social variables and the returns offered by the video game and eSports exchange-traded fund (ESPO). The results show that the influence of social factors is weaker than the influence of financial factors. There is a significant inverse relationship between market volatility and ESPO returns and a highly significant relationship between ESPO returns and gold returns.

September 16, 2020 (Journal of Air Transport Management)

Risks, resilience, and pathways to sustainable aviation: A COVID-19 perspective

Stefan Gossling.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jairtraman.2020.101933>

This paper discusses the COVID-19 pandemic as an opportunity to reconsider the foundations of the global aviation system. Pandemics and aviation's contribution to climate change are examples of long-standing negative factors that have been ignored in assessments of aviation's economic performance. Stefan questions whether a return to business-as-usual is desirable. The volume growth model pioneered by industry and aviation proponents may have to be replaced with an alternative model of a smaller air transport system that is economically less vulnerable and causing less negative environmental impacts.

September 9, 2020 (Journal of Public Economics)

Economic uncertainty before and during the COVID-19 pandemic

Dave Altig, Scott Baker, Jose Maria Barrero et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpubeco.2020.104274>

The authors consider several economic uncertainty indicators for the US and UK before and during the COVID-19 pandemic, such as stock market volatility, Twitter chatter about economic uncertainty, uncertainty about business growth. They find all indicators show huge uncertainty jumps in reaction to the pandemic and high volatility in share prices